

of tillers and panicles per unit area, and reduced number of filled spikelets per panicle.

Regardless of the rice variety used,

good weed control is essential to obtain high grain yield. It is particularly important to weed early-maturing varieties early to minimize yield reduction. The

study also indicated that application of nitrogen fertilizer can increase yields of dry-seeded rice in weed-free conditions,

Weeds of Chingleput district, Tamil Nadu

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A sound knowledge of weed flora and their possible effects on a crop is essential

when planning weed control measures. Published reports on flora are available, but weed flora on agricultural lands changes. We have compiled a list of all wetland and dryland weeds that grow at PES Tirur (see table).

Tirur receives 1,200 mm average-annual rainfall, most of it during September-

November (northeast monsoon season). Almost no rain falls from January to April. Rice, in wetland and dryland culture, is the major crop. Groundnut and millets also are grown. Weed problems are more severe in drylands than in wetlands. Dry weather from January to April favors the spread of dryland weed seeds that germinate when rains begin in July-August. Rainfed rice grown during July-August face serious weed competition. Weeds that grow during the fallow season cause weeds to spread in wetlands.

Agricultural weeds of Tirur, India.

Dryland weeds

<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> Linn..	Aizoaceae
<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> Linn..	Amaranthaceae
<i>Digera arvensis</i> Forsk.	Amaranthaceae
<i>Gomphrenn celosioides</i> Mart.	Amaranthaceae
<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i> Dc. (Linn.)	Asteraceae
<i>Eclipta alba</i> (Linn.) Hassk..	Asteraceae
<i>Erigeron asteroides</i> Roxb.	Asteraceae
<i>Flaveria australasica</i> Hook.	Asteraceae
<i>Lactuca runcinata</i> Dc.	Asteraceae
<i>Tridax procumbens</i> Linn.	Asteraceae
<i>Vernonia cinerea</i> (Linn.) Less..	Asteraceae
<i>Vicoa indica</i> Dc..	Asteraceae
<i>Heliotropium indicum</i> Linn..	Boraginaceae
<i>Trichodesmo indicum</i> R. Br..	Boraginaceae
<i>Eleome viscosa</i> Linn.	Capparidaceae
<i>Gynandropsis pentaphylla</i> (Linn.) Dc.	Capparidaceae
<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> (Linn.) Linn..	Convolvulaceae
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> Linn.	Cyperaceae
<i>Fimbristylis littoralis</i> Gaudich.	Cyperaceae
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> Linn.	Euphorbiaceae
<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> Linn.	Euphorbiaceae
<i>Glinus oppositifolius</i> Linn. A. Dc.	Molluginaceae
<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> Linn..	Nyctaginaceae
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> (Linn.) Beauv..	Poaceae
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (Linn.) Link..	Poaceae
<i>Eragrostis interrupta</i> (Lam.) Doell. var. Koenigii. Stapf	Poaceae
<i>Panicumrepens</i> Linn	Poaceae
<i>Sporobolus coromandelianus</i> (Retz.) Kunth.	Poaceae
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> Linn.	Portulacaceae
<i>Hedyotis umbellata</i> Linn. Lam.	Rubiaceae
<i>Rysanthes veronicaefolia</i> Urban.	Scrophulariaceae
<i>Physalis minima</i> Linn.	Solanaceae
<i>Corchorus olitorius</i> Linn.	Tiliaceae

Wetland weeds

<i>Eclipta alba</i> (Linn.) Hassk..	Asteraceae
<i>Cyperus bulbosus</i> Vahl.	Cyperaceae
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> Linn.	Cyperaceae
<i>Fimbristylis miliaceae</i> (Linn.) Vahl.	Cyperaceae
<i>Bergia capensis</i> Linn.	Elatinaceae
<i>Spirodela polyrhiza</i> (Linn.) Schleid.	Lemnaceae
<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> Linn..	Lythraceae
<i>Rotala densiflora</i> (Roth.) Koehne.	Lythraceae
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L. Rich.) Pers.	Poaceae
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (Linn.) Link..	Poaceae
<i>Panicum repens</i> Linn..	Poaceae
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i> Gaertn.	Sphenocleaceae

Soil and crop management

Age of dhaincha, green matter, and nitrogen economy in rice

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In recent work at the PAU farm, burying 2-month-old dhaincha (*Sesbania aculeata*) 1 day before transplanting saved up to 120 kg N/ha. But the period for raising a dhaincha crop varies with time of rice transplanting, generally spread over almost a month in Ludhiana.

The effect of age of dhaincha on amount of green matter added and N economy was tested in kharif 1981. Soil of the experimental plot was loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with a percolation rate of 6 mm/hour. It had pH 8.4, EC 0.15 mmho/cm, 0.34% organic carbon, 0.06% N, 8 µg/gram KCl-extractable NH₄⁺-N, and 8 µg/gram NO₃-N.

Dhaincha was sown at 15-day intervals from 3 May to 3 June to attain 60, 45, and 30-day-old crops at rice transplanting. Phosphorus at 60 kg P₂O₅/ha was applied at sowing. Check plots